

The Impact of Shopee Quality Service for The Customers Satisfaction of Making Purchases in Marimbuns Village Pematang Siantar Year 2022/2023

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ABSTRACT

This type of research is quantitative. This research was carried out to find out how the quality of Shopee service affects customer satisfaction carried out in the Tong Marimbun Pematang Siantar sub-district. The subjects of this research were the people of Tong Marimbun sub-district, taking 80 people. So the total number of people who use the Shopee application was taken, a total sample of 80 respondents was used. Data collection was carried out using library research methods, documentation, questionnaires. The results of the questionnaire have been tested for validity and reliability, in the form of normality assumptions. Data analysis techniques use normality test techniques, simple regression heteroscedicity tests , f tests and t tests. By using the Statistical Product and Service Solution (SPSS) program. The research results showed that the proposed hypothesis was accepted because it showed positive and significant hypothesis test results. This means that Shopee's online service quality has a positive and significant effect on consumer satisfaction in Tong Marimbun Pematang Siantar sub-district.

INTRODUCTION

The internet is currently considered important in human life . Because there are many uses for today's technology . In 2022 - 2023 internet users in Indonesia will reach 215.63 million. This number increased by 2.67 % compared to the previous period which was 210.03 million users. This proves that the development of technology and communication is increasing every year in Indonesia. Lifestyles are starting to change, people are starting to like everything that is instant, one option is online shopping. Online shopping is a process where consumers directly buy goods and services from a seller interactively and in real-time without any intermediary media.

Application of information communication technology that can be used to support the sales system, namely e-commerce. What is meant by e-commerce is sales made through electronic media. Describing e-commerce as a situation where the process of buying and selling products is carried out electronically by consumers and from company to company using a computer as an intermediary in business transactions. E-commerce brings big business opportunities (such as product sales and online service provision) and growth income.

However, even with the increasing number of customers shopping online, e-commerce is proving to be more complicated than the traditional way of selling in business. Improving the quality of e-commerce services is considered one of the keys to success or failure in the e-retailing supply chain. Technological developments have a growth The large number of online figures has encouraged intense competition, including increasing e-commerce sales. View customer experience as something important for online sellers. e-commerce has become a business alternative in the modern era which is in line with increasingly dynamic market conditions and competitive competition, resulting in changes in consumer behavior.

Shopee Pay has an electronic money service feature as a payment method used when shopping online at Shopee, it can also be used to pay for offline transactions at Shopee merchants and mini markets. Consumers can also find out the remaining products to be purchased and consumers can also monitor products that have been ordered from order to delivery.

However, the use of vouchers, free cream fees and cashback can only be used using certain payment methods and consumers cannot choose the delivery service they only want when purchasing a product, instead Shopee automatically chooses the delivery service by adjusting the estimated time and delivery capacity options. so that orders can be received more quickly.

Many sellers sell the same product on Shopee, it is possible that the price consumers find is cheaper but for similar items. Often the price set by sellers for consumers makes consumers feel hesitant to buy the product because the price does not match the benefits and quality of the product, plus the delivery courier chosen automatically by Shopee means consumers cannot choose the desired delivery courier, this will have an impact. to consumer satisfaction because product delivery costs will be more expensive than usual, and can even be more expensive than the price of the product the consumer wants to buy.

S hopee provides appropriate and appropriate services. Companies want to understand consumer expectations and provide satisfactory service. Where if consumers are satisfied with the services provided, then consumers tend to compare them with other companies' services. In situations where dissatisfied consumers who have used the product or experienced the services they have purchased are concerned that the product performance turns out to be not all consumers feel that it does not meet expectations.

However, the Shopee company also provides that if a customer has a complaint or question, they can contact their customer service, then the question or complaint will be responded to immediately by Shopee .

By being aware of the existing information, in this research the author chose Shopee as the research object, with the aim of knowing the quality of service on Shopee satisfaction. Based on the background above, I as a writer am interested in highlighting this problem as my title " *The Impact of Shopee Quality Service for The Customers Satisfaction of Making Purchases in Marimbuns Village Pematang Siantar Year 2022/2023* "

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

1. Shopee Service Quality

Quality is something that must be done to provide good services. The quality of a product or service is the main part of a company's strategy in order to achieve sustainable excellence, either as a leader or as a strategy to continue to grow. According to Kotler and Keller (2016: 37) that product quality is a product's ability to carry out its functions , This capability includes durability, reliability, accuracy, which is obtained by the product as a whole. Gronroos in Mukarom and Laksana (2018:80) can explain that service is the activity of a series of activities that are invisible (cannot be touched) which occur as a result of interactions between consumers and employees or other things provided by the service provider company.

2. Customer Satisfaction

Consumers are every person who obtains goods or services that are used for certain purposes. According to Kotler and Keller (2020:1) consumer behavior is the study of how individuals, groups and organizations choose, buy, use and how goods, services, ideas or experiences satisfy their desires. Fatihudin and Firmansyah (2019:206) consumer satisfaction is a measurement or indicator of the extent to which customers or users of company products or services are very happy with the products or services received. Consumer satisfaction is dynamic, meaning that consumer expectations for a product/service will change over time.

METHODS

The type of research carried out is descriptive quantitative research. This research is descriptive research because it aims to describe the facts and characteristics of a particular population or area systematically, factually and thoroughly. According to Sugiyono (2017:11) that "Quantitative Research can be interpreted as A research method based on positivist philosophy, used to research certain populations or samples, data collection using research instruments, quantitative/statistical data analysis, with the aim of testing the hypothesis that has been applied.

Based on the researcher's title "The Influence of Shopee Service Quality on Consumer Satisfaction in Making Purchases in Tong Marimbun District, Pematang Siantar." This research was carried out in Tong Marimbun District, Pematang Siantar . Especially in the Tong Marimbun Pematang Siantar sub-district community. And the research time will be adjusted to the data and information required. The population in this study was the Marimbun community with 30 people aged 17-20 years and 50 people aged 21-40 years. So the population used in this research was 80 people. The sample used in the research was the entire population, namely 80 people.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Results

Respondent Identity

Characteristics of Respondents Based on Age

Table 1
CHARACTERISTICS OF RESPONDENTS BASED ON AGE
Age

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 17-20	30	37.5	37.5	37.5
21-29	16	20.0	20.0	57.5
30-39	24	30.0	30.0	87.5
40	10	12.5	12.5	100.0
Total	80	100.0	100.0	

From table 1 above, it shows that the 80 respondents sampled in this study were known to be aged 17-40 years. There were 30 respondents aged 17-20 (37.5%), 16 people aged 21-29 years (20%), 24 people aged 30-39 years (30%), 10 people aged 40 years (12.5%). Thus, the largest number of respondents who have shopped at Shopee are aged 30-39 years.

Characteristics Based on Gender

Table 4.2
CHARACTERISTICS BASED ON GENDER
Gender

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid man	20	25.0	25.0	25.0
Woman	60	75.0	75.0	100.0
Total	80	100.0	100.0	

From Table 2 above, it shows that female respondents dominated in this study, namely 60 people (75%), and male respondents amounted to (20%). Thus, it can be concluded that the people in Tong Marimbun sub-district who have shopped at Shopee are mostly women.

Research Instrument Trial Results

Instrument Validity Test

The validity test in this research used SPSS version 22 and Ms. Excel 2007. The level used to test the validity of the instrument is 0.05 %. Based on the results of the validity test, 30 people were tested by the Marimbun community with a total of 20 questions.

Based on the table above, items that have a table value ≥ 0.361 are valid questionnaires, namely items 1,2,3,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,14,15,16,17,18, 19. And conversely, items that have an r table correlation value ≤ 0.361 are questionnaire items that are

invalid or declared invalid so it can be concluded that the validity test of the Service Quality instrument is declared valid and invalid.

Instrument Reliability Test

For the questionnaire reliability criteria, if $r_{count} > r_{table}$ with a significant level ($\alpha = 0.05$) then the questionnaire is said to be reliable. However, if $r_{count} \leq r_{table}$ then the questionnaire is considered to have no reliability. If the *Cronbach Alpha value* is > 0.60 it is said to be reliable, but if the *Cronbach Alpha value* is < 0.60 it is said to be unreliable.

From the data obtained, it is known that the *Cronbach Alpha* obtained was $0.794 > 0.60$. From the results of calculating the reliability of the influence of Shopee service quality, it can be concluded that the research instruments used are reliable.

From the data obtained, it is known that the *Cronbach Alpha* obtained was $0.764 > 0.60$. From the results of consumer satisfaction reliability calculations, it can be concluded that the research instruments used are reliable.

Data Normality Test

Figure 1. Normal Probability P-Plot Curve

Based on the test results of the p-plot graph, it shows the conclusion that the data is spread around the diagonal line, so the data is declared normal. This can be seen in figure 1 above.

Multicollinearity Test

Table 1. Multicollinearity Test Results

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	Q	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1 (Constant)	39,027	6,929		5,633	,000		
SERVICE	,372	,112	,352	3,322	,001	1,000	1,000

(Source: Data processed by SPSS researchers 2022)

a. Dependent Variable: SATISFACTION

The assumption of Tolerance and Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) can be stated that if $VIF > 10$ and Tolerance value < 0.10 then multicollinearity occurs, and if $VIF < 10$ and Tolerance value > 0.10 then multicollinearity does not occur. Based on table 4.7, Tolerance > 0.10 and Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) < 10 , it can be concluded that there are no symptoms of multicollinearity in the data.

Heteroscedasticity Test

Figure 2 Scatterplot curve

Based on Figure 2, it can be seen that the points are spread above and below the number 0 on the Y axis. Thus it can be concluded that heteroscedasticity does not occur.

Simple Analysis Test

Table 3 Simple Test Results

Coefficients ^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	Q	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	39,027	6,929		5,633	,000
Influence of service quality	,372	,112	,352	3,322	,001

(Source: Data processed by SPSS researchers 2022)

a. Dependent Variable: consumer satisfaction

Based on table 3 (Simple Linear Regression Calculation Results) above, the simple linear regression equation can be seen as follows:

The coefficients of the simple linear regression equation above can be interpreted as a constant regression coefficient of 39,027, indicating that if the Shopee Service Quality variable has a value of zero or constant, it will increase consumer satisfaction by 0.372 units, which will increase consumer satisfaction by 0.372 units or 37.2%.

t test

The partial test (t) is used to determine whether the hypothesis used is accepted or rejected, with a confidence level of 95% or $\alpha=5\%$, with the following conditions :

1. If $t_{count} > t_{table}$, then the independent variable has an effect on the dependent variable.
2. If $t_{count} < t_{table}$, then the independent variable has no effect on the dependent variable.

Table 4 t test results

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	39,027	6,929		5,633	,000
Influence of service quality	,372	,112	,352	3,322	,001

(Source: Data processed by SPSS researchers 2022)

a. Dependent Variable: consumer satisfaction

Based on variable 4, the calculated value of the Influence of Shopee Service Quality (5.633) is greater than the t table (1.66462) and the t calculated value of the influence of Shopee Service Quality (3.322) is greater than the t table (1.66462). Thus, the independent variable has a significant effect on the related variable.

F test

The F test is carried out to find out whether the independent variables together have an influence on the dependent variable. In this case, Fcount is compared with Ftable with the following conditions :

1. If $F_{count} > F_{table}$, then H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted
2. If $F_{count} < F_{table}$, then H_1 is rejected and H_0 is rejected.

Table 5 F Test Results

ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	857,588	1	857,588	11,037	.001 ^b
Residual	6060,599	78	77,700		
Total	6918,187	79			

(Source: Data processed by SPSS researchers 2022)

a. Dependent Variable: consumer satisfaction

b. Predictors: (Constant), influence of service quality

Based on table 5, it is found that the Fcount value (11.037) is greater than the Ftable value (3.11). This indicates that the research results reject H_0 and accept H_1 . Thus, simultaneously the influence of Shopee's service quality influences the variable of consumer satisfaction in purchasing in Tong Marimbun District, Pematang Siantar with a significant level of influence. This gives the meaning of the hypothesis which

states that the influence of Shopee's service quality and consumer satisfaction simultaneously influences the variables that influence Shopee's service quality on Consumer satisfaction in purchasing in the Tong Marimbun Pematang Siantar sub-district is acceptable

Coefficient of Determination Test

Table 6 Coefficient of Determination Test Results

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	,352 ^a	,124	,113	8,815

(Source: Data processed by SPSS researchers 2022)

a. Predictors: (Constant), influence of service quality

The accepted coefficient value R square in table 4.13 is known to be 0.124 which means 12.4 % . Variables on the Influence of Shopee Service Quality on Consumer Satisfaction When Making Purchases in Tong Marimbun District, Pematang Siantar. Meanwhile , 87.6 % is the influence of other variables not examined in this research.

The results of the analysis above have implications regarding the influence of Shopee service quality on consumer satisfaction in making purchases in the Tong Marimbu Pematang Siantar sub-district. This is important in order to increase the variable contribution of the Influence of Shopee Service Quality on Consumer Decisions in Making Purchases by 12.4%.

Discussion

The results of the classical assumption test, the above normality test are the main requirements to be able to proceed to the multiple regression analysis test with the data having a normal distribution and a significance level of > 0.05 . In the learning media variable, the influence of Shopee Service Quality on Consumer Satisfaction in Making Purchases in Tong Marimbun District, Pematang Siantar has a normal distribution between variables with a significant level of 0.06 > 0.05, and based on Figure 4.2, the normal p-plot curve can be seen that The distribution of data is around the diagonal line and follows the diagonal direction, so the values are standardized and meet the normality assumption.

The results of the multicollinearity test show that Tolerance > 0.10 and Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) < 10, based on table 4.7 it is known that the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) value is 1,000 < 10 and the Tolerance value is 0.10 > 0.10, so it can be concluded that the data does not have symptoms. multicollinearity.

The results of the heteroscedasticity test based on figure 4.2 show that the dots are spread above and below the number 0 on the Y axis. Thus it can be concluded that there is no heteroscedasticity, and based on table 4.8 it is known that the significant value of the Influence of Shopee Service Quality (0.215) and Consumer Satisfaction (0.496) it can be concluded that there are no symptoms of heteroscedasticity because the significance value must be greater than 0.05.

Based on table 4.9, it is known that the constant value (a) is 61.22, while the value of the influence of shopee service quality (b) is 61.81 for consumer satisfaction, so the regression equation is:

$$Y = a+bx$$

$$Y =39.027+372$$

The coefficients of the simple linear regression equation above can be interpreted as a constant regression coefficient of 39,027, indicating that if the Shopee Service Quality variable has a value of zero or constant, it will increase consumer satisfaction by 0.372 units, which will increase consumer satisfaction by 0.372 units or 37.2%.

calculated t value of the influence of Shopee service quality (5.633) is greater than the t_{table} (1.66462). Based on the results obtained, H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted for the variable influencing Shopee service quality. Thus, partially the influence of Shopee service quality influences consumer satisfaction in making purchases in the Tong Marimbun Pematang Siantar sub-district. And the calculated t value of consumer satisfaction (3.322) is greater than the t_{table} (1.66462). Based on the results obtained, H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted for the consumer satisfaction variable. Thus, partially the influence of Shopee service quality influences consumer satisfaction in making purchases in the Tong Marimbun sub-district.

Partially, the shopee service quality variable is more dominant than consumer satisfaction. This can be seen from table 4.10 where Shopee's service quality has the highest value, namely 5,633. This means that the Shopee service quality variable has a greater influence on consumer satisfaction when making purchases in the Tong Marimbun sub-district.

The F test results based on table 4.11 show that the calculated F value (11.037) is greater than the t_{table} F value (3.11). This indicates that the research results reject H_0 and accept H_1 . Thus, simultaneously the influence of Shopee service quality influences the consumer satisfaction variable in making purchases in the Tong Marimbun sub-district of Pematang Siantar with a significant level of influence.

The coefficient of determination R Square value in table 4.13 is known to be 0.124, which means 12.4 % of the variable influence of Shopee service quality on consumer satisfaction in making purchases in the Tong Marimbun subdistrict of Pematang Siantar. Meanwhile, 87.6 % is the influence of other variables not examined in this research.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results of data analysis and discussion regarding the Influence of Shopee Online Service Quality on Consumer Satisfaction among Unismuh Makassar Economics and Business Students, the results of this research can be concluded that Service Quality has a positive and significant effect on Consumer Satisfaction. As seen in the SPSS 22 processing results, there is a strong relationship between Service Quality and Consumer Satisfaction. This shows that if service performance is good and in line with consumer expectations, consumer satisfaction will increase.

FURTHER STUDY

Based on the research results which state that there are positive and significant results of the influence of Shopee's online service quality on consumer satisfaction in the Tong Marimbun Pematang Siantar sub-district community, the author suggests to the parties responsible, Online Shopee should be able to maintain the quality of service that has provided satisfaction for Consumer. Especially the service of refunds because goods are damaged or not according to the order, returns of goods because they are damaged or not according to the order, customer service that handles complaints well and quickly, availability of a 24-hour call center to serve consumers

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The author realizes that in writing this thesis, there are still many shortcomings. For this reason, with all humility the author hopes for suggestions and constructive criticism for the perfection of writing this thesis research proposal in the future so that it can provide direction to the author in the next steps of writing.

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